

Train Accident Prediction using Sensor Data and Machine Learning

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Abstract— The goal of this study is to improve the effectiveness and security of train reservation experiences by recommending an advanced machine learning (ML) based security solution. To analyze a lot of data and find security vulnerabilities, the system uses ML algorithms. The suggested system specifically uses a logistic regression model to forecast train accidents based on information gathered from multiple sensors, including temperature, smoke, and accelerometer sensors. The system can forecast train accidents with high accuracy and detect potential security concerns by analyzing these sensor data, allowing for quick preventive action.

Keywords- Machine Learning, Security System, Train Booking, logistic regression, Railway Accidents, Sensors.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mobility and access to goods and services are two of the transport sector's most crucial roles in today's society. Trains are one of the best, safest, and most environmentally friendly ways of transportation. Train accidents are a serious problem for both railway operators and passengers since they can result in enormous losses in terms of both lives and property. Only a few of the potential problems include human error, derailments, and collisions. It is essential to identify and anticipate potential hazards to lower the likelihood of train accidents.

The utilization of sensor data as a source of information has lately become commonplace in several industries, including transportation. Sensors are used in the railway industry to collect data on environmental factors, track conditions, and train movements. To find potential dangers and avoid mishaps, this data can be analyzed. The safety and dependability of train travel have been significantly improved by the transportation sector. However, train mishaps continue to happen, causing substantial material and human losses. Many methods, including sensor-based monitoring systems, automated warning systems, and prediction models based on machine learning, have been suggested to increase train safety. Machine learning-based prediction models have demonstrated good outcomes in predicting and preventing train accidents among various strategies. In this article, we provide a machine learning-based method for forecasting train accidents using sensor data.

Our suggested approach analyses sensor data and predicts the likelihood of railway accidents using a logistic regression technique. In machine learning for binary classification tasks, where the result is either 0 or 1, the logistic regression approach is a popular choice. The proposed model uses various sensor data including acceleration, temperature, and vibration to identify potential train accidents. By analyzing these data, the model can effectively identify the patterns and trends that lead to train accidents. The model can then alert the train operators to take appropriate preventive measures to avoid potential accidents.

II. LOGISTIC REGRESSION

The supervised machine learning approach known as logistic regression is commonly used to address binary classification problems. This statistical method can predict a binary outcome variable by employing one or more predictor variables. The technique is called "logistic" because it uses a logistic function to model the connection between the predictor components and the outcome variable. The technique is called "logistic" because it uses a logistic function to model the connection between the predictor components and the outcome variable.

Logistic regression is a technique used in generalised linear models (GLMs). A member of the GLM model family can be used to illustrate the relationship between one or more predictor variables and a response variable. The response variable in a logistic regression model is binary. That is, it can only take one of two forms (for example, yes or no, true or false, etc.). Furthermore, the predictor variables could be categorical, continuous, or a combination of both. The logistic regression approach employs the logistic function to model the connection between the predictor elements and the outcome. The logistic regression approach employs the logistic function to model the connection between the predictor elements and the outcome. This makes it ideal for modeling a binary response variable.

A. WORKING ON LOGISTIC REGRESSION

A logistic function is used in logistic regression to model the relationship between the input components and the likelihood of the output variable. The logistic function, commonly known as the sigmoid function, forms an S-shaped curve based on the values of the input variables that can be used to predict the likelihood of the output variable.

As follows is a description of the logistic function:

$$1 / (1 + e^{-z}).$$

where e is the base of the natural logarithm and z is the linear combination of the input variables and their assigned weights. Any z value can be transformed into a probability between 0 and 1 using the logistic function.

The logistic regression model generates the best weight values for the data by reducing the difference between the expected and actual values. A cost function is used to compute the difference between expected and actual values. The cross-entropy loss function is identical to minimising the cost function and is commonly stated as the data's negative log-likelihood.

On a set of labelled data, the logistic regression model is trained. with each example including a set of input variables and a binary output variable. The model modifies its weights during training by employing an optimisation strategy like gradient descent in order to optimise the cost function. Once trained, the model can be used to forecast the likelihood of an outcome given a collection of input factors.

Fig 1(Logistic Regression Graph)

Overall, logistic regression is a potent and understandable machine-learning technique that may be applied to issues involving binary and many classes of categorization. The link between the predictor variables and the result variable is modelled using a logistic function. It is simple to comprehend how the algorithm predicts outcomes since the coefficients of the logistic function may be understood as the effect of each predictor variable on the outcome variable.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Hamad Alawad, Sakdirat Kaewunruen, and Min An et.al [1], in their paper titled "A Deep Learning Approach Towards Railway Safety Risk Assessment" states that railway safety is a critical aspect of public transportation, and risk management is vital in ensuring the safety of passengers and their assets. The authors propose a novel framework for risk management in railway systems using computer vision and pattern recognition. They employed a convolutional neural network (CNN) to identify risks in railway stations, which are known for their dynamic and complex conditions. The use of AI technology is crucial for risk management in railway systems since accidents and injuries still occur despite extensive efforts by industry associations and researchers.

The proposed model better captures fall, slip, and trip (FST) events in stations and obtains more accurate motion data. The proposed method offers a beneficial way to obtain more accurate motion data and detect adverse conditions as soon as possible. The benefits of using deep learning in risk management include real-time ability, integration of multiple subsystems, and improved effectiveness of operations. The proposed CNN-based method provides real-time, accurate visual monitoring of risks in railway stations to assist safety or risk management operations, which are reflected in passenger services. The method is more suitable for real-world conditions and is cost-effective. The paper presents an innovative approach to ensuring the safety of passengers and their assets in railway systems. The authors' contributions to the field of AI technology for risk management in railway systems have significant potential to impact the railway industry positively.

Hamad Alawad, Sakdirat Kaewunruen, and Min An et.al [2], in their paper titled "Learning From Accidents: Machine Learning for Safety at Railway Stations" explores the application of machine learning (ML) in improving safety at railway stations. The paper presents a case study that focuses on fatal accidents at railway stations and utilizes the decision tree (DT) method to analyze and predict the traits of passengers affected by such accidents. The critical contribution of this study is to highlight the potential of ML in improving safety and risk management in the railway industry.

The paper notes that accidents at railway stations remain a critical aspect of the overall railway system, and despite various safety measures, accidents still occur. Therefore, the paper argues that it is necessary to learn from these errors and improve conventional methods by utilizing the latest technology such as ML to analyze accidents and enhance safety systems. The paper demonstrates the applicability of DTs in analyzing and predicting passenger traits affected by accidents at railway stations. The supervised algorithm employed in the study performs accurately and can be used effectively to address state-of-the-art applications using ML. Additionally, employing a variety of algorithms using ML provides robust and beneficial analysis of the history of safety records.

The paper concludes by noting that the integration of ML in railway station safety is a challenging task, and more in-depth research is required. The shortage of data available to apply ML remains a challenge for researchers. However, the paper recommends that the railway industry can choose any safety datasets that have been recorded to teach an ML application with a range of analytical methods.

Overall, the paper offers a useful literature assessment of the use of machine learning for safety and risk management in the railway business. It emphasizes how ML has the ability to enhance security and lower accidents at train stops.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

There is a lot of potential for forecasting train accidents and enhancing train safety by using sensor data and machine learning. We will concentrate on employing three different types of sensors in this suggested methodology: temperature, accelerometer, and smoke sensors.

These sensors, which will be dispersed throughout the train, will gather information on temperature variations, smoke emissions, and changes in acceleration. The gathered sensor data will undergo preprocessing to eliminate any outliers, noise, and redundant features before being converted into a machine learning-friendly format. As the main machine-learning algorithm for forecasting train accidents, logistic regression will be used. Given a collection of input features, the supervised learning technique known as logistic regression can forecast the likelihood that an event will occur.

In the machine learning part, first, the program imports the necessary modules: train_test_split and Logistic Regression from sci-kit-learn, pandas for data manipulation, and MySQL. Connector for database access.

```
import mysql.connector
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.linear_model import LogisticRegression
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
import time
```

The data is then read from the CSV file "sensor_data.csv" via pandas' read_csv() method. Using the train_test_split() function, the data is then divided into training and testing sets. The data is then separated into training and testing sets using the train_test_split() function. The training data consists of two columns, "temperature" and "accelerometer", and the target variable "accident". The testing set is 20% of the data, which is specified by the test_size parameter.

```
# Read train data from a CSV file
train_data = pd.read_csv('train_data.csv')

# Split the train data into features and labels
X_train = train_data[['temperature', 'accelerometer_x', 'smoke']]
y_train = train_data['accident']
```

After the data has been split, the program trains a logistic regression model using the Logistic Regression() function from sci-kit-learn. The model is then fitted to the training set of data using the fit() technique. The score() method is used to determine the model's accuracy, which is then output to the console.

```
# Plot
import seaborn as sns

sns.pairplot(train_data, x_vars=['temperature', 'accelerometer_x', 'smoke'], y_vars='accident')

# Create and fit a logistic regression model
model = LogisticRegression(random_state=0)
model.fit(X_train, y_train)

# Connect to the database
cnx = mysql.connector.connect(user='root', password='', host='localhost', database='train3')

# Create a cursor
cursor = cnx.cursor()
```

The predict() method is then used by the programme to define a new data point (80, 1) for forecasting accidents using the learned model. The predictions are printed on the console.

The MySQL-connector-python package is then used by the programme to establish a connection to a MySQL database.

By passing the user, password, host, and database name as inputs to the connect() method, the connection is made. A cursor object is created using the cursor() method. The program executes a SELECT statement on the "trains" table in the database using the execute() method. Then, all rows of data returned by the SELECT statement are fetched using the fetchall() method. The data is then printed to the console after being iterated through.

```
# Connect to the database
cnx = mysql.connector.connect(user='root', password='', host='localhost', database='train3')

# Create a cursor
cursor = cnx.cursor()
```

```
# Execute a SELECT statement to retrieve temperature, accelerometer, smoke, and status data
while True:
    time.sleep(3)
    query = 'SELECT sid, temperature, accelerometer_x, smoke, status FROM sensor_data'
    cursor.execute(query)
    rows = cursor.fetchall()
    # Iterate through the rows and print the data
    for row in rows:
        print(f"ID: {row[0]}")
        print(f"Status: {row[4]}")
```

Finally, the program closes the cursor and connection to the database using the close() method.

```
if y_pred[0] == 1:
    print("Accident")
    update_query = f'UPDATE sensor_data SET status=2 WHERE sid={row[0]}'
    cursor.execute(update_query)
else:
    print("No Accident")
    update_query = f'UPDATE sensor_data SET status=1 WHERE sid={row[0]}'
    cursor.execute(update_query)

cnx.commit()

# Close the cursor and connection
cursor.close()
cnx.close()
```

Train	Temperature in oC	Vertical Acceleration	Smoke	Status	Action
TIR-1004 Maveli Express	16	30	13	Danger, stop the train	[Icons]
TIR-1001 Tiruvandrum - Chennai Duronto Express	20	14	4	Normal condition	[Icons]

Fig2: Status Updation(Accident or no Accident)

Figure[Fig2] shows that when the accident occurred it will be reflected in the status as “ Danger” or “Safe “.

Fig 3:Hardware Architecture

+ Options		sid	temperature	accelerometer_x	smoke	status
□	✎ Edit	1	10	10	10	0

From the Figure[Fig 3]

- **Microcontroller:**
The brain of the hardware module
E.g.:
 - Arduino UNO
 - Arduino nano
 - Raspberry Pi
 - Esp32
- **Accelerometer:** Will give 3-axis acceleration accurately
- **MQ2 smoke sensor:** Will give details if any smoke/gas presence is detected.
- **WIFI/GSM:** Wireless Data transmission between train and server.

Fig 4: Process Flow

From the Figure[Fig 4]

1. Hardware data to the server with status=0
2. Python code: requesting the fresh data
3. Process the data
4. Update the DB according to the prediction

ML part works:

1. Training:

2. Testing

We will use sensor data collected from the train's sensors to evaluate the likelihood of a train accident occurring in real time once the logistic regression model has been trained. If the model predicts a high probability of a train accident, a warning will be provided to the train operator and other relevant parties, allowing them to take the required precautions to avoid the accident.

The suggested methodology's overarching goal is to show how sensor data and machine learning may be used to predict train accidents and improve train safety. We will be able to precisely forecast the probability of a train accident taking place based on the information gathered from the accelerometer, temperature, and smoke sensors, and perhaps prevent accidents from taking place by using logistic regression as the machine learning technique.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the ability to forecast railway accidents using sensor data and machine learning, particularly logistic regression, can be significantly assisted. It is feasible to predict potential dangers and avoid disasters by gathering information from a range of sensors, such as temperature, smoke, and accelerometers, and analysing it with machine learning algorithms. Using logistic regression, it is particularly possible to quantify the likelihood of an event occurring, allowing for proactive protection of both staff and passenger safety. Even if there are difficulties in putting such a system into practice, such as the requirement for trustworthy sensor data and suitable training data for the machine learning algorithms, the advantages of increased safety and decreased accident rates make it a potential path forward.

VI. REFERENCES

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